

Review of *Euplectromorpha* Girault and *Euplectrus* Westwood (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) from Kenya, with description of two new species

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the Kenyan species of *Euplectromorpha* Girault and *Euplectrus* Westwood. *Euplectromorpha emeljanovi* Yefremova, formerly known only from Ethiopia, has been collected from the Kenyan Highlands (Nairobi) and from an isolated patch of indigenous forest next to Lake Victoria in western Kenya. These two occurrences represent the southernmost records of the species and the southernmost record of the genus from continental Africa. Fourteen species of *Euplectrus* are recorded from Kenya: 11 species described by Ferrière (*E. aburiensis*, *E. cinctiventris*, *E. epiplemae*, *E. fuscipes*, *E. laphygmae*, *E. liparidis*, *E. nigrescens*, *E. nigroclypeatus*, *E. rufiventris*, *E. singularis*, *E. turneri*), *E. scapus* Yefremova, and two described herein as new (*Euplectrus icipeensis* sp. n. and *E. subsphaericus* sp. n.). We also redescribe the females of *E. nigroclypeatus* and *E. turneri*, and the males of *E. aburiensis* and *E. singularis*. An identification key is provided for all 14 species of the genus *Euplectrus* found in Kenya.

KEYWORDS: Afrotropical, Chalcidoidea, Eulophinae, Eulophini, Hymenoptera, identification key, new species, parasitoids.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Euplectromorpha* Girault, 1913 is poorly represented in the Afrotropical Region. *Euplectromorpha pallida* Bouček, 1966 from the Ivory Coast remained the only confirmed species of the genus until *Euplectromorpha emeljanovi* Yefremova, 2003 was described from Ethiopia. Other African species described by Ferrière (1941) in the genus *Euplectromorpha* as *E. variegata* Ferrière, 1941, *E. striolata* Ferrière, 1941, *E. kiambuensis* Ferrière, 1941 and *E. kampalana* Ferrière, 1941 were later transferred to *Platyplectrus* Ferrière, 1941 (Yefremova & Copeland 2023).

The Afrotropical fauna of *Euplectrus* Westwood, 1832 includes 25 species (UCD Community 2023): *Euplectrus aburiensis* Ferrière, 1941, *E. acutigaster* Zhu & Huang, 2003, *E. bebourensis* Risbec, 1957, *E. bicolor* (Swederus, 1795), *E. brevitarsis* Ferrière, 1941, *E. castaneus* Risbec, 1957, *E. ceresensis* Ferrière, 1941, *E. cinctiventris* Ferrière, 1941, *E. epiplemae* Ferrière, 1941, *E. euplexiae* Rohwer, 1921, *E. fulvicoxis* Ferrière, 1941, *E. fuscipes* Ferrière, 1941, *E. hargreavesi* Ferrière, 1941, *E. laphygmae* Ferrière, 1941, *E. leonae* Risbec, 1951, *E. medanensis* Crawford, 1911, *E. milii* Risbec, 1951, *E. nigrescens* Ferrière, 1941, *E. nigroclypeatus* Ferrière, 1941, *E. phy-*

tometrae Risbec, 1951, *E. platyhypenae* Howard, 1885, *E. rufiventris* Ferrière, 1941, *E. seychellensis* Ferrière, 1941, *E. singularis* Ferrière, 1941 and *E. turneri* Ferrière, 1941.

Euplectrus laphygmae is the only species of this genus previously recorded from Kenya (Gerling & Limon 1976). Among the neighbouring countries, *E. laphygmae* is known from Uganda, Sudan (Ferrière 1941) and Tanzania (Fry 1989). The presence of *E. bicolor* in the neighbouring Somalia has been noted (Bouček & Askew 1968) but the species has not been found in Kenya. In the present study, new distribution records, descriptions of new species, re-descriptions of species and an identification key to the *Euplectrus* species from Kenya are provided. No new host information is recorded for species from Kenya in this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material from Kenya was collected by RSC from many sites throughout the country (see [Supplementary material](#)) as part of an ongoing survey and inventory project that began in 1996 (e.g. Miko *et al.* 2014; Delvare *et al.* 2018; Kim *et al.* 2018). Nearly all specimens were collected in Townes-style Malaise traps (Townes 1972) or, infrequently,

Figures 1–8: Collection sites: (1) Elsamere Conservation Centre, Lake Naivasha, disturbed lacustrine forest. (2) Gede Forest, secondary forest. (3) Kakamega Forest. (4) Kiboko Sanctuary. (5) Sosoma area. (6) Ukasi Hill. (7) Muhaka Forest. (8) Nguruman.

in 6-metre Malaise traps. Other than Malaise traps (MT), the material was collected by light traps (LT) and sweeping. Examples of representative sampling sites include the following.

Elsamere Conservation Centre (Fig. 1), Lake Naivasha, disturbed lacustrine forest, elevation 1913 m a.s.l., where *Euplectrus icipeensis* sp. n. and *E. laphygmae* were collected.

Gede Forest (Fig. 2), secondary forest, elevation 19 m a.s.l. This is part of the East African Coastal Forests hotspot, where *E. laphygmae*, *E. rufiventris* and *E. turneri* were collected.

Kakamega Forest (Fig. 3), elevation 1620 m a.s.l. This is a large upland forest in western Kenya. The indigenous vegetation shows strong affinities to the Guineo-Congolian rain forests, of which Kakamega Forest is the easternmost example. *Euplectrus icipeensis* sp. n., *E. liparidis* and *E. nigroclypeatus* were collected.

Kiboko Sanctuary (Fig. 4), elevation 925 m a.s.l. In contrast to the surrounding xeric vegetation, the strip of the indigenous forest at Kiboko is supported by the high water table and run off of a nearby more or less permanent stream. *Euplectrus laphygmae*, *E. rufiventris* and *E. turneri* were collected.

Sosoma area (Fig. 5), elevation 501 m a.s.l. This is a dry, deciduous *Acacia/Commiphora* woodland. The image was taken during the dry season. *Euplectrus scapus* and *E. turneri* were collected.

Ukasi Hill (Fig. 6), elevation 615 m a.s.l., is one of several hilly outcrops or inselbergs found in xeric eastern Kenya, remnants of the ancient Precambrian rocks of the basement system that underlie the entire country (Cole 1950). The Malaise trap was set up at the base of the hill. The image was taken during the rainy season. *Euplectrus aburiensis* and *E. laphygmae* were collected.

Muhaka Forest (Fig. 7), elevation 50 m a.s.l. This is a small and relatively wet indigenous forest on the south coast of Kenya. Like the Gede Forest, it is a part of the East African Coastal forests hotspot. It is also a *kaya* (sacred) forest and maintained as such by village elders, affording it some protection. *Euplectrus turneri* was collected here.

Nguruman (Fig. 8), elevation 723 m a.s.l. This is a dry, hot *Acacia* woodland located at the base of the Nguruman escarpment and near a seasonal stream. The image was captured in the rainy season. *Euplectrus aburiensis* and *E. rufiventris* were collected.

Morphological terminology follows Gibson (1997) and Burks *et al.* (2025). The following abbreviations are used in this paper: F1–F4 – 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th funiculars; Gt_{n+1} – gastral terga; mv – marginal vein; OOL – minimum distance between eye margin and adjacent posterior ocellus; pmv – postmarginal vein; POL – minimum distance between the posterior ocelli; smv – submarginal vein; stv – stigmal vein; T1, T2 – 1st and 2nd tarsomeres; tbs₁ – longer hind tibial spur; tbs₂ – shorter hind tibial spur.

Measurements in millimetres (mm) are used for body parts. For all other dimensions, relative measurements are used. Observations and measurements were made using a Leica M 125. For images of individual specimens, multiple photographs were captured using a Macropod macrophotography system (MacroscopicSolutions.com) with a CANON 6D Mark II camera body and either a CANON MP-E 65 mm macro lens, or a CANON EF 70–200 zoom lens fitted with a Mitutoyo 7.5×, 10× or 20× lens. Zerene stacking software was used to produce the final images, which were cropped and adjusted for contrast and brightness using Photoshop CS6 Extended software.

Holotypes of the new species are deposited in the insect type collection of the National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi.

Diagnoses, figures, distribution and host records, where known, are presented, along with descriptions of the new species. New country records for species are denoted by an asterisk.

The examined material is deposited in the following institutions: ICIPE – International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya; NHM – Natural History Museum, London, UK; NMK – National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi, Kenya; SMNH – Steinhardt Museum Natural History Tel Aviv University, Israel; USNM – National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC, USA.

TAXONOMY

Family Eulophidae Westwood, 1829
Subfamily Eulophinae Westwood, 1829
Genus *Euplectromorpha* Girault, 1913

Euplectromorpha Girault, 1913: 276. (Type species: *Euplectromorpha unifasciata* Girault, 1913; orig. des.)

Neoplectrus Ferrière, 1940: 134. (Type species *Neoplectrus bicarinatus* Ferrière, 1940, des. by Lin (1963)). Synonymized with *Euplectromorpha* by Bouček (1988: 634).

Diagnosis. Propodeum with two submedial carinae connected anteriorly by raised basal cup, forming a medial areola; petiole transverse; tbs₁ reaching half-length of Gt₁ (Wijesekara & Schauff 1994).

Identification. A key to 15 species (eight from Africa, six from the Malayan Archipelago and one from Europe) was published by Ferrière (1941), though several of these have since been transferred to *Platyplectrus* (Yefremova & Copeland 2023). Keys are also available to four *Euplectromorpha* species of Sri Lanka (Wijesekara & Schauff 1994), nine species in China (Zhu & Huang 2001), four species in India (Narendran 2011) and five keyed species from Thailand, Vietnam and Malaysia (Yefremova 2015a).

Euplectromorpha emeljanovi Yefremova, 2003
Figs 9–12

Euplectromorpha emeljanovi Yefremova, 2003: 135.

Diagnosis. Female. Pronotum with black, transverse carina. Propodeum with two strong submedial carinae, these diverging slightly from base to apex of propodeum (Fig. 11). tbs_1 1.04× as long as T1. Scutellum rugulose with sublateral grooves. Antenna (Fig. 9). F1 1.3× as long as pedicel, F2 1.2× shorter than F1, clava 1.7× as long as F4. Head yellow-orange with dark brown, forked macula from toruli to postocellar line (Fig. 12). Body mostly yellow (Figs 9, 10), propodeum dark brown, gaster yellow, except apical segments brownish. All coxae yellow (Fig. 9). **Male.** Antenna. F1 2.2× as long as pedicel, F1 1.27× as long as F2, clava 2.0× as long as F4.

Material examined. ETHIOPIA • 1♀; Jinka; 20 Aug. 2010; Z. Yefremova; yellow pan trap; SMNH.

KENYA – **Nairobi Prov.** • 1♀; Kasarani, ICIPE campus; 1.22444° S, 36.89874° E; 1609 m; 21–26 Dec. 2019; R. Copeland; MT behind Bee Health building, degraded shrub/grassland; ICIPE. – **Nyanza Prov.** • 1♀; Ungoye, ICIPE field station; 0.61500° S, 34.09146° E; 1145 m;

29 May – 12 Jun. 2017; R. Copeland; MT in seasonally swampy forest; ICIPE.

Distribution. Ethiopia (Yefremova 2003); *Kenya.

The diversity of *Euplectromorpha* is low in the Afrotropical Region, with a single species from West Africa (*E. bicarinatus* (Ferrière, 1940)) and *E. emeljanovi* from eastern Africa. In Kenya, *E. emeljanovi* was collected in a MT set in seasonally swampy forest alongside Lake Victoria and in Nairobi, in a peri-urban setting with the MT set in a badly degraded meadow composed largely of adventitious weedy vegetation with the occasional bush. The Nairobi specimen is the southernmost representative of the genus in the Afrotropical Region.

Host. Unknown.

Genus *Euplectrus* Westwood, 1832

Euplectrus Westwood, 1832: 128.

A complete synonymy can be found in Hansson *et al.* (2015), Hansson and Schmidt (2018), and Noyes (2019).

Figures 9–12: *Euplectromorpha emeljanovi* Yefremova, female: (9, 10) lateral and dorsal habitus; (11) propodeum dorsal (arrows point to submedial carinae); (12) head frontal.

Type species. *Euplectrus maculiventris* Westwood, 1832, by monotypy.

Diagnosis. Female. Head with paired long setae on vertex; eyes bare. Mandibles small, without teeth covered by several setae and not meeting with each other. Scutellum lacking longitudinal grooves or fovea; propodeum with distinct medial carina and semicircular or triangular cup. Hind coxa enlarged and globose; tbs_1 as long as T1 and T2 combined, or slightly less. Fore wing large, smv with 4–5 setae. Body with black or yellow markings, legs yellow, sometimes hind coxae and femora brown, antennae yellow or brownish, gaster brown with yellow markings (Yefremova 2017). **Male** similar to female, but smaller, antennal scape broader at middle than in female, in some species markedly swollen (Yefremova 2007; Hansson *et al.* 2015).

Distribution. Cosmopolitan (Hansson *et al.* 2015).

Identification. A key to 14 African species was published by Ferrière (1941). Keys are also available to the 11 *Euplectrus* species of Sri Lanka (Wijesekara & Schauff 1994), 25 species in China (Zhu & Huang 2003), 37 species in India (Narendran 2011), 90 species from northern Costa Rica (Hansson *et al.* 2015), 25 species in key of *Euplectrus* from Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam and Malaysia (Yefremova 2017), and 13 European species (Hansson & Schmidt 2018).

The keys for the 14 species are given separately for females and males because sexual dimorphism occurs in six species: *E. aburiensis*, *E. epiplemae*, *E. laphygmae*, *E. scapus*, *E. singularis* and *E. subsphaericus* sp. n.

Key to the *Euplectrus* species from Kenya

Females

- 1 Hind coxae and often hind femora brown (Figs 25, 28).....2
 - Hind coxae and hind femora yellow3
- 2 All coxae and femora brown (Fig. 25).....*E. fuscipes*
 - Only hind coxae and hind femora brownish (Fig. 28).....
.....*E. icipiensis* sp. n.
- 3 Mid lobe of mesoscutum with complete medial groove with complete or partial medial carina along bottom (Figs 20, 43)4
 - Mid lobe of mesoscutum with incomplete medial groove and with partial medial carina along bottom (Fig. 56).....5
- 4 Medial groove deep with complete medial carina on bottom (Figs 19, 20); clypeus black (Fig. 21); scape 4.8× as long as broad, F1 1.5× as long as pedicel (Fig. 21)
.....*E. cinctiventris*
 - Medial groove not deep and not complete, with medial carina along bottom 1/3 posterior part of groove (Fig. 43); clypeus reddish (Fig. 44); scape 5.6× as long as broad, F1 1.1× as long as pedicel (Fig. 44) *E. nigrescens*
- 5 POL/OOL=4.0–4.5, diameter of posterior ocelli large, 3.0× longer than OOL (Figs 55, 56).....*E. scapus*

- POL/OOL=3.0–3.2, diameter of posterior ocelli small 1.3× shorter than OOL (Fig. 34)6
- 6 Head black (Fig. 70) or dark brown (Fig. 48).....7
 - Head with yellow markings (Fig. 36)8
- 7 F4 subquadrate, scape whitish (Figs 67, 70)..... *E. turneri*
 - F4 1.9–2.2× as long as broad, scape yellow (Fig. 48).....
.....*E. nigroclypeatus*
- 8 F1–F4 equal to each other9
 - F1–F4 not equal to each other10
- 9 Antennal clava 3.6–3.8× as long as broad (Fig. 36); gaster yellow with posterior 1/2 black (Figs 32, 34).... *E. laphygmae*
 - Antennal clava 1.8× as long as broad (Fig. 50); gaster entirely yellow (Fig. 52)*E. rufiventris*
- 10 F1=F2=F3; petiole 1.75–2.0× as long as broad (Figs 37, 39)
..... *E. liparidis*
 - F1, F2 and F3 not equal to each other; petiole <1.75× as long as broad11
- 11 F1 1.2× as long as pedicel (Fig. 13). Gaster completely yellow (Fig. 13)*E. aburiensis*
 - F1 as long as pedicel12
- 12 Head and clypeus brown; POL/OOL=2.8; antennal clava 3.0× as long as broad (Fig. 63)..... *E. subsphaericus* sp. n.
 - Head black and clypeus brownish yellow; POL/OOL <2.0; antennal clava <3.0× as long as broad (Fig. 23).....13
- 13 POL/OOL=1.3; mid lobe of mesoscutum strongly reticulate, without medial groove; legs yellow (Fig. 23)... *E. epiplemae*
 - POL/OOL=1.75; mid lobe of mesoscutum areolate with medial groove 1/2 of its length; fore and mid coxae whitish (Fig. 61).....
..... *E. singularis*

Males

- 1 Scape swollen (Figs 55, 64).....2
 - Scape not swollen (Figs 38, 40).....4
- 2 Scape grossly swollen, subsphaerical (Figs 64, 65); mesoscutum with neither groove nor medial carina.....
..... *E. subsphaericus* sp. n.
 - Scape swollen but of different shape (Fig. 62); mesoscutum with incomplete medial groove, but lacking medial carina..3
- 3 Scape slightly swollen with ellipsoid shape, 2.4× as long as broad (Figs 60, 62), clava 4.0× as long as broad; mid lobe of mesoscutum with groove on apical 1/3 of its length
.....*E. singularis*
 - Scape strongly swollen with oblong shape, 2.0× as long as broad (Figs 54, 55, 57), clava 2.6× as long as broad; mid lobe of mesoscutum with groove on apical 2/3 of its length
.....*E. scapus*
- 4 Mid lobe of mesoscutum with complete medial groove with complete or partial medial carina on bottom5
 - Mid lobe of mesoscutum without medial groove or with medial groove only indicated posteriorly (as in Fig. 43).....6
- 5 Scutellum reticulated with raised cells, mesoscutum irregularly transverse striate, medial groove with partial medial carina on apical 1/3 of groove (Fig. 43); clypeus dark reddish (Figs 41, 42)..... *E. nigrescens*
 - Scutellum only superficially reticulated, mesoscutum coarsely reticulated, medial groove deep with complete medial carina on bottom (as in female, Fig. 20); clypeus black (Fig. 18)
.....*E. cinctiventris*
- 6 Hind coxae brown (Fig. 29).....7

- Hind coxae light yellow (Figs 33, 38)8
- 7 All coxae and femora dark brown (as in female, Fig. 25)
.....*E. fuscipes*
- Only hind coxae and hind femora brown (Fig. 29).....
.....*E. icipiensis* sp. n.
- 8 Head dark brown or black.....9
- Head with yellow markings10
- 9 F4 1.6× as long as broad, clava 2.3× as long as broad and
1.6× as long as F4 (Fig. 48).....*E. nigroclypeatus*
- F4 1.1× as long as broad, clava 1.9–2.0× as long as broad and
2.1× as long as F4 (Fig. 68)..... *E. turneri*
- 10 Head entirely yellow (Fig. 33) except vertex brownish
.....11
- Head brown with yellow or brownish clypeus and with brown
cheeks12
- 11 F1–F4 equal to each other, 2.0–2.2× as long as broad, clava
3.6× as long as broad; gaster yellow with posterior ½ black
(Figs 33, 35).....*E. laphygmae*
- Only F3=F4, 2.8× as long as broad, clava 3.2× as long as
broad; gaster completely yellow (Figs 14, 15).....
.....*E. aburiensis*
- 12 Petiole 1.75–2.0× as long as broad (Fig. 38)..... *E. liparidis*
- Petiole 1.4–1.5× as long as broad or less.....13
- 13 Scape 2.6× as long as broad; clypeus yellow; gaster brownish
(Fig. 22) *E. epiplemae*
- Scape 4.0× as long as broad; clypeus reddish; gaster entirely
yellow (Fig. 49) *E. rufiventris*

Euplectrus aburiensis Ferrière, 1941

Figs 13–16

Euplectrus aburiensis Ferrière, 1941: 38.

Diagnosis as given by Ferrière (1941): “Body black, head of female with face below the antennae and cheeks yellow; head of male entirely yellow; abdomen yellowish, only the sides near base and petiole black, antenna brown, scape yellow; legs yellow” (Figs 13, 16) and by Yefremova (2007): “F1 1.2× as long as pedicel; pedicel 2.0× as long as broad. Axillae, scutellum and propodeum smooth, TS1 equal to T1 and T2 together, clypeus and cheeks yellow, gaster yellow”.

Additional diagnosis. Male. Mesoscutum areolate, without medial groove. POL 1.25× as long as OOL. Antenna. F1 and F2 2.0–2.4× as long as broad, F3 and F4 2.87× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented, 3.2× as long as broad and 1.8× as long as F4. Fore wing 2.5× as long as broad.

Redescription. Male. Body length 1.0–1.2 mm.

Colour. Head yellow (Figs 14, 15), eyes dark pink, ocelli dark yellow, antenna yellow, scape, pedicel and F1 pale yellow, tegulae dark yellow, gaster yellow, legs yellow (Fig. 14).

Figures 13–16: *Euplectrus aburiensis* Ferrière: (13, 14) female and male lateral habitus; (15) male, dorsal habitus; (16) female, head frontal.

Head. Malar sulcus absent (Fig. 14). Eyes asetose. POL 1.25× as long as OOL. Antenna. Pedicel 1.8× as long as broad, F1 2.0× as long as broad, F2 2.4× as long as broad, F3 and F4 2.8× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented 3.2× as long as broad and, 1.8× as long as F4. F1 1.1× as long as pedicel, F3=F4.

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mesoscutum strongly areolate without medial groove, scutellum reticulate, axillae alutaceous, propodeum superficially reticulate, smooth, with medial carina, callus with two rows, first with 3 long setae, second with 2 long setae. Fore wing 2.5× as long as broad. smv with 3 long setae. Speculum $\frac{2}{5}$ along mv and open. smv(90):mv(60):pmv(37):stv(22); pmv 1.7× as long as stv. Basal cell bare.

Metasoma. Petiole short and conical, 1.1× as long as broad. Gaster 1.2× as long as broad. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines.

Material examined. Syntype: GHANA •♂; Aburi, Gold Coast; 1 Jan. 1939; G.S. Cotterell; ex geometrid; *Euplectrus* (AT+PLT) *aburiensis* Ferrière, det. Z. Bouček, 1974; NHM013457192.

KENYA – **Coast Prov.** •12♀; Taita Hills, Vuria Forest; 3.41428°S, 38.29178°E; 2162 m; 30 Nov. – 14 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. – **Eastern Prov.** •1♂; Mulu Musingila farm; 2.11412°S, 38.23989°E; 689 m; 27 Dec. 2016 – 10 Jan. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, farmland near small seasonally wet area; ICIPE. •1♀, same data; 25 Dec. 2017 – 12 Jan. 2018. •5♀, 1♂; same data; 1–25 Dec. 2017; ICIPE. •5♀, 1♂; same data; 11–25 May 2018; ICIPE, SMNH. •3♀, 1♂; same data; 30 Oct. – 13 Nov. 2018; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 1–15 Apr. 2017; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 27 Apr. – 11 May 2018; SMNH. •18♀; Nyambene Hills, Itieni Forest, at bottom; 0.24433°N, 37.87016°E; 2142 m; 13–27 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; ICIPE, SMNH. •4♀; Samburu Nat. Reserve, nr Ewaso Ng'iro River; 0.56797°N, 37.53563°E; 874 m; 4–18 Sep. 2007; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest, nr KWS Headquarters; ICIPE, SMNH. •1♀; Marsabit Forest; 2.32167°N, 37.98409°E; 1418 m; 18 May – 1 Jun. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, near Ahmed gate, indigenous forest; SMNH. •1♀; base of Ukasi Hill; 0.82002°S, 38.54378°E; 615 m; 29 Apr. – 5 May 2018; R. Copeland; MT, *Acacia Commiphora* savanna; ICIPE. – **Rift Valley Prov.** •1♂; Nguruman, nr Sampu River, 1.90117°S, 36.05040°E; 723 m; 31 Dec. 2011 – 13 Jan. 2012, R. Copeland; MT; SMNH. •8♀; Matthews Range; 1.00661°N, 37.38631°E; 1006 m; 29 Nov. – 12 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, Sarara campsite, shrubland; ICIPE, SMNH. •5♀; same data; 15–29 Nov. 2015; ICIPE.

Distribution. Ghana, West Africa (Ferrière 1941); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Geometridae (Lepidoptera) (Ferrière 1941).

Euplectrus cinctiventris Ferrière, 1941
Figs 17–21

Euplectrus cinctiventris Ferrière, 1941: 36.

Diagnosis was given by Ferrière (1941) and Zhu and

Huang (2003), without a redescription Yefremova (2017) provided the following diagnosis and redescribed the species: “Female. ... Head (Figs 17, 18, 21). POL 1.8× as long as OOL. F1 1.7× as long as broad. F1=F2=F3. F2 and F3 1.6× as long as broad. F3 1.3× as long as F4. Clava 1.9× longer than F4 and 2.1× as long as broad”.

Additional characters. Mesoscutum coarsely reticulated, medial groove deep and complete with complete medial carina along bottom (Fig. 20).

Ferrière (1941) wrote: “Male. Similar; scape broadened and curved toward tip, the funicle joints narrower and a little longer; abdomen smaller, triangular”. Body length 1.6–1.7 mm.

Material examined. Syntype: UGANDA •♀; Kampala; 14 Jan. 1930; H. Hargreaves; ex caterpillars on grass lumundi; *Euplectrus cinctiventris* det. Ch. Ferrière; NHM010370945.

KENYA – **Coast Prov.** •1♀; Arabuko-Sokoke Forest; 3.30958°S, 39.96538°E; 80 m; 9–23 Nov. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; SMNH. – **Eastern Prov.** •1♀; Samburu Nat. Reserve, nr Ewaso, Ng'iro River; 0.56797°N, 37.53563°E; 874 m; 12–26 Jun. 2007; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest, next to KWS Headquarters; SMNH. •1♀; same data; 24 Jul. – 7 Aug. 2007; R. Copeland; SMNH. •1♀; Kasaala area; 2.07836°S, 38.22517°E; 733 m; 22 May – 5 Jun. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. – **Rift Valley Prov.** •1♀; Saiwa Swamp Nat. Park, nr campsite; 1.09417°N, 35.11833°E, 1882 m; 29 Jan. – 12 Feb. 2006; R. Copeland; MT next to permanent upland swamp; ICIPE. •1♀; Chorlim, base of Mt Elgon; 1.03149°N, 34.84780°E; 1887 m; 20 May – 3 Jun. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, *Acacia* riverine woodland; ICIPE. •1♀; Matthews Range, Sarara campsite; 1.00661°N, 37.38631°E; 1006 m; 15–29 Nov. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland; ICIPE.

MALI •1♀; Kéniéroba; 12.10722°N, 8.33278°E; 330 m; 30 Sept. 2014; V. Kravchenko; SMNH.

Distribution. South Africa, Uganda (Ferrière 1941); China, Dominican Republic, Papua New Guinea, South Africa, Uganda (Zhu & Huang 2003); Vietnam (Yefremova 2017); *Kenya, *Mali.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus epiplemae Ferrière, 1941
Figs 22–24

Euplectrus epiplemae Ferrière, 1941: 38.

Diagnosis. Female. Body length 1.5–1.8 mm. Ocelli small, POL 1.3× as long as OOL. Scape 4.8× as long as broad, pedicel equal to F1, F1=F2, F3=F4, clava 2-segmented, 2.8× as long as broad and 1.4× as long as F4. Hind femur thickened in both sexes 2.0× as long as broad or a bit less. Mesoscutum strongly reticulate in middle, without medial carina posteriorly (Fig. 22), scutellum finely reticulate (Fig. 23). Petiole 1.4×

Figures 17–24: (17–21) *Euplectrus cinctiventris* Ferrière, female: (17, 18) lateral and dorsal habitus; (19) dorsal head and thorax with medial carina (arrowed); (20) mesoscutum with complete groove and medial carina at bottom (arrowed); (21) female, head frontal. (22–24) *E. epiplemae* Ferrière: (22) male, lateral, and (23) female, dorsal habitus; (24) female, head, frontal, and thorax and gaster lateroventral.

as long as broad, rugulose, with two spines. Body black, clypeus yellowish brown, antenna brownish, scape, pedicel and F2–F4 whitish (Fig. 24), legs yellow. **Male.** Body length 1.3–1.5 mm. Scape 2.6× as long as broad (Fig. 22).

Material examined. Syntype: UGANDA • ♀; Kampala; 21 Dec. 1933; H. Hargreaves; ex caterpillars on coffee; NHM010370950.

KENYA – **Coast Prov.** • 1♂; Kasigau Mtn, indigenous forest; 3.82667° S, 38.64982° E; 1117 m; 13–27 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to spring in forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasigau Mtn, bottom of forest; 3.82080° S, 38.64178° E; 737 m; 30 Jun. – 14 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. • 1♂; Buda Forest; 4.46109° S, 39.40446° E; 98 m; 28 Aug. – 11 Sep. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; SMNH.

Distribution. Belgian Congo, South Africa, Uganda (Ferrière 1941); *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus fuscipes Ferrière, 1941
Figs 25–27

Euplectrus fuscipes Ferrière, 1941: 35.

Diagnosis. Female and Male. Body length 1.7 mm. POL 2.8× as long as OOL. Two long setae between lateral ocelli and two shorter near occiput. Fore wing 2.4× as long as broad. Pedicel 1.6× as long as F1, F2 1.4× as long as F1, F2 subequal to both F3 and F4. Clava 2.8× as long as broad. Mesoscutum strongly reticulated without medial groove, scutellum finely reticulate, propodeum smooth and shiny (Fig. 26). Body black. Face brown with black clypeus (Figs 25, 27). All coxae black, femora dark brown, hind tibiae light brown (Figs 25, 26).

Material examined. Syntype: UGANDA • ♀; Kampala; 3 Sep. 1917; C. Gowday; *Euplectrus fuscipes* Ch. Ferrière; NHM 010370923.

ANGOLA • 1♀; 10 mi SE Mongua; 16 Oct. 1966; E.S. Ross & K. Lorenzen; SMNH.

KENYA – **Rift Valley Prov.** • 1♀; Saiwa swamp Nat. Park, nr Campsite; 1.09417° N, 35.11833° E; 1882 m; 12–26 Feb. 2006; R. Copeland; MT next to permanent upland swamp; ICIPE.

UAE – **Sharjah** • 1♀, 1♂; Sharjah Desert Park; 25.17° N, 55.42° E; 21 Mar. – 29 Sep. 2005; A. van Harten; LT; SMNH.

Distribution. Ivory Coast (Risbec 1951); Uganda (Ferrière 1941); *Angola, *Kenya, *UAE.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus icipeensis sp. n.
Figs 28–31

LSID. urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A0F070CE-7ED3-48C7-A1B7-C295EF759159.

Etymology. This species is named after the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), on whose campus the holotype was collected as part of a survey and inventory project documenting the diversity of East African insects.

Diagnosis. Female. Body length 1.4–1.8 mm. Mesoscutum superficially reticulated without medial groove and medial carina (Fig. 30). POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Antenna (Fig. 31). F1, F2, F3 subequal to each other. Clava 2.2× as long as broad. Body mostly black, head black, clypeus brownish, legs yellow, except hind coxae black. **Male** (Fig. 29). Body length 1.4–1.8 mm. POL 1.7× as long as OOL. F1, F2, F3 and F4 subequal. Clava 2.1× as long as broad. Petiole 1.5× as long as broad. Body, head, clypeus and hind coxae black, hind femora brown dorsally.

Euplectrus icipeensis most closely resembles *E. fuscipes*, except that in *E. icipeensis* only the hind coxae and femora are brown (Figs 28, 29) while in *E. fuscipes* all femora and coxae are dark brown.

Description. Female. Body length 1.4–1.8 mm (HT 1.4 mm).

Colour. (Figs 28, 30). Body mostly black, head black, clypeus dark yellow or brownish, eyes grey, ocelli light yellow; antenna yellow, tegulae dark yellow, gaster yellow on Gt_{2–4}, black on Gt_{5–7}, and brownish at base, fore and mid legs yellow, hind legs yellow (except coxae and femora brownish).

Head. Malar sulcus absent. Two long pairs of setae present between posterior ocelli. Eyes asetose (Fig. 31). POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Antenna. Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad (Fig. 28), with 2 long and 2 short brown setae. F1=F2=F3, F4 1.1× shorter than F3, all of them 2.2–2.3× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented 2.2× as long as broad and 1.5–1.6× as long as F4 (Fig. 28).

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mesoscutum superficially reticulated without medial groove and medial carina (Fig. 30), scutellum longitudinally reticulate, axillae alutaceous, propodeum superficially reticulate, smooth, with medial carina, callus with two rows of setae, first with 6 setae, second with 2 setae. Fore wing 2.5× as long as broad, smv with 3 long setae. Speculum small along pterostigma. smv(20): mv(33.5):pmv(18):stv(10.2); pmv 1.7× as long as stv. Costal cell with a single long seta and a row of 8 setae close to marginal vein. Hind wing rounded apically. Hind legs with two spurs; tbs₁ 1.3× as long as T1 and 1.3× as long as tbs₂.

Metasoma. Petiole 1.3–1.4× as long as broad, reticulate. Gaster 2.2× as long as broad. Ovipositor not extended.

Male. Body length 1.35–1.8 mm.

Colour similar to female. POL 1.7× as long as OOL. Scape 3.9–4.0× as long as wide. Pedicel 2.2× as long as broad, with 2 long and 2 short brown setae.

Figures 25–32: (25–27) *Euplectrus fuscipes* Ferrière, female: (25, 26) lateral and dorsal habitus; (27) head frontal. (28–31) *E. icipeensis* sp. n.: (28, 29) female and male, lateral habitus; (30) female, dorsal habitus; (31) female, head frontal. (32) *E. laphygmae* Ferrière, female, lateral habitus.

F1=F2=F3=F4; all funiculars 1.5× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented 2.0× as long as broad and 1.8× as long as F4 (Fig. 29). Petiole 1.5× as long as broad, reticulate. Gaster 1.5× as long as broad. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines.

Holotype. KENYA – Nairobi Prov. • ♀; ICIPE campus, Kasarani; 1.22317° S, 36.89653° E; 1600 m; 24 Feb. – 10 Mar. 2014; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub/grassland; NMK.

Paratypes. KENYA – Central Prov. • 2♂; Kamwana Forest; 0.40009° S, 37.38403° E; 1842 m; 14–28 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; SMNH. • 1♂; same data; 28 Mar. – 11 Apr. 2016; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. – Nairobi Prov. • 1♀; ICIPE campus, Kasarani; 1.22317° S, 36.89653° E, 1600 m; 8–15 Apr. 2014; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub-/grassland; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 20–22 May 2014; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub-/grassland; NMK. • 1♀; same data; 3–10 Jun. 2014, R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub-/grassland; ICIPE. • 1♂; ICIPE campus, Kasarani; 1.22317° S, 36.89653° E; 1600 m; 10–17 Jul. 2014; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub-/grassland; ICIPE.

Additional material examined. KENYA – Coast Prov. • 1♂; Taita Hills, Chawia Forest; 3.47908° S, 38.34162° E; 1614 m; 26 Dec. 2011 – 9 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; SMNH. • 1♂; Taita Hills, Ronge Forest; 3.21° S, 38.25° E; 1200 m; 25 Oct. – 8 Nov. 1999; Taita Biodiversity Project; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Ngangao Forest; 3.21239° S, 38.17985° E; 1780 m; 1–5 Feb. 1998; Taita Biodiversity Project; MT; NMK. • 1♀; Kasigau Mtn; 3.82667° S, 38.64982° E; 1117 m; 13–27 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to spring in forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Chawia forest; 3.47908° S, 38.34162° E; 1614 m; 13–27 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; SMNH. – Eastern Prov. • 1♀; Nyambene Hills, Itieni Forest; 0.23417° N, 37.87635° E; 2507 m; 25 May – 8 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest at top of hill; NMK. • 1♂; Kasaala area; 2.07836° S, 38.22517° E; 733 m; 8–12 Jan. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; NMK. • 1♂; Kibwezi Forest; 2.41687° S, 37.95388° E; 945 m; 6–20 Apr. 2016; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; SMNH. – Rift Valley Prov. • 1♂; nr Malu Farm, Naivasha; 0.62884° S, 36.42969° E, 1909 m; 25 Sep. – 11 Oct. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in understory of Yellow *Acacia* patch; SMNH. • 1♂; Tsavo West Nat. Park, riverine woodland; 2.99615° S, 38.45988° E; 464 m; 9–23 Feb. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo River; ICIPE; 1♂; same data; 4–18 Nov. 2008; ICIPE. • 1♀; Saiwa Swamp Nat. Park, nr Campsite; 1.09417° N, 35.11833° E; 1882 m; 12–26 Feb. 2006; R. Copeland; MT next to permanent upland swamp; ICIPE. • 1♂; Elsamere Conservation Centre, Lake Naivasha; 0.81306° S, 36.31585° E; 1913 m; 22 Aug. – 5 Sep. 2019; R. Copeland; MT, lacustrine forest remnant; SMNH. • 1♂; Chorlim, base of Mt Elgon; 1.03149° N, 34.84780° E; 1887 m; 28 Jun. – 12 Jul. 2017; R. Copeland; MT in *Acacia* riverine woodland; SMNH. – Western Prov. • 1♂; Kakamega Forest, nr KFS Headquarters; 0.23742° S, 34.86607° E; 1620 m; 16–30 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; SMNH.

Distribution. Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus laphygmae Ferrière, 1941
Figs 32–36

Euplectrus laphygmae Ferrière, 1941: 40.

Diagnosis. Mesoscutum without medial groove, reticulate (Fig. 34). Scutellum finely reticulate. POL 1.2× as long as OOL. Ocelli very small compared with other species of *Euplectrus* (Fig. 34). Two setae between posterior ocelli. Fore wing (Fig. 32) 2.8× as long as broad. Pedicel 1.3× shorter than F1. F1–F4 equal to each other. Petiole subquadrate. Face brown with yellow lower face, clypeus and genae (Fig. 36). All legs yellow (Yefremova 2017). Body length 1.6–2.0 mm. **Male.** Head of male bright yellow, except vertex brown (Fig. 35). Digitus with two spines. Mesoscutum areolate. POL 1.2× as long as OOL. Scape 3.3× as long as broad, pedicel 2.2× as long as broad, F1–F4 equal to each other and 2.2× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented 3.2× as long as broad and 1.3× as long as F4. Fore wing 2.6× as long as broad (Fig. 33). Body length 1.3–1.8 mm.

Material examined. Syntype: MALAWI – Nyasaland • 1♀; Zomba; 2500 m; Apr. 1936; C. Smee; ex "*Laphygma* [*Spodoptera*] *exempta*"; NHM010370915. Note: the specimen bears a purple lectotype label with "Bouček 1974" on the reverse side but no valid lectotype designation has ever been published.

KENYA – Central Prov. • 1♀; Kamwana Forest; 0.40009° S, 37.38403° E; 1842 m; 15–29 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♂; Mucagara farm; 0.46297° S, 37.3584° E; 1563 m; Dec. 2016 – Feb. 2017; R. Copeland; mini MT, mixed maize, coffee; SMNH. • 1♀; Mary Muriuki farm; 0.49250° S, 37.38822° E; 1457 m; 2 Jun. – 28 Jul. 2018; R. Copeland; yellow pan traps in farmland nr Nyamindi River; ICIPE. – Coast Prov. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Mbololo Forest; 3°20.00' S, 38°26.85' E; 1550 m; 21–30 Jun. 1999; Taita Biodiversity Project; MT; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Vuria Forest; 3.41428° S, 38.29178° E; 2162 m; 14–28 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 2♀; Taita Hills, Chawia Forest; 3.47908° S, 38.34162° E; 1614 m; 18 Sep. – 2 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 2–16 Oct. 2011; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Ngangao Forest, 3.36100° S, 38.34186° E; 1848 m; 29 Nov. – 12 Dec. 2011, R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest, ICIPE. • 1♂; Vuria Forest; 3.41428° S, 38.29178° E; 2162 m; 21 Aug. – 4 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 11–25 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasigau Mtn, 3.82700° S, 38.64875° E; 1065 m; 28 Dec. 2011 – 11 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT next to campsite in forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Diani Beach area; 4.27559° S 39.59337° E; 10 m; 12–26 Dec. 2013; R. Copeland; MT, shrub land off Diani Beach road; SMNH. • 1♂; Arabuko-Soko Forest; 3.30958° S; 39.96538° E, 80 m; 31 Dec. 2014 – 13 Jan. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; SMNH. • 1♀; same data;

21 Jul. – 3 Aug. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 1–15 Sep. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 17–31 Jan. 2016; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Gede Forest; 3.30946° S, 40.01941° E; 19 m; 24 Jun. – 7 Jul. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 21 Jul. – 3 Aug. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 7–21 Jul. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Macha Forest; 3°26.81'S, 38°21.76'E; 1520 m; 21–29 Apr. 1999; Taita Biodiversity Project; MT; ICIPE. – **Eastern Prov.** • 3♀, 1♂, base of Ukasi Hill; 0.82103° S, 38.54443° E; 613 m; 7–21 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, *Acacia/Commiphora* savanna; ICIPE. • 2♀; Kasaala area; 2.07836° S, 38.22517° E; 733 m; 25 Dec. 2014 – 8 Jan. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. • 3♀, same data 17–31 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 26 Jan. – 9 Feb. 2016; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. • 1♀; same data; 23 Feb. – 8 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 5–19 May 2018; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. • 1♀; same data 5–19 May 2018, R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. • 10♀; base of Endau Mtn, 531 m; 1.30026° S, 38.52805° E; 18 May – 1 Jun. 2018; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; SMNH. • 1♀; same data; 15–29 Oct. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous

forest; SMNH. • 5♀; same data; 26 Nov. – 10 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 3♀; same data; 10–24 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 23 Jan. – 6 Feb. 2017, R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kibwezi Forest; 2.41649° S, 37.95560° E; 925 m; 25 Oct. – 6 Nov. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 5–19 Nov. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♂; same data; 30 Dec. 2017 – 13 Jan. 2018; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 10♀; same data; 5–19 Nov. 2017, R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kiboko Sanctuary; 2.20331° S, 37.71430° E; 925 m; 3–17 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; SMNH. – **Rift Valley Prov.** • 1♀; Marich Pass Field Station, 1.53633° N, 35.45800° E; 917 m; 17–31 Aug. 2005; R. Copeland; MT, low canopy riverine forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 30 May – 12 Jun. 2005; R. Copeland; MT, low canopy riverine forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Saiwa Swamp Nat. Park, nr Campsite; 1.09417° N, 35.11833° E; 1882 m; 29 Jan. – 12 Feb. 2006; R. Copeland; MT next to permanent upland swamp; SMNH. • 1♀; Masai Mara Nat. Reserve; 1.54638° S, 35.30672° E; 1756 m; 25 Jul. – 2 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT next to dry stream bed; SMNH. • 1♀; Tsavo West Nat. Park, riverine woodland; 2.99615° S, 38.45988° E; 464 m; 30 Jul. – 12 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo River; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 12–26 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo River; SMNH. • 1♀; Olorgesailie, Nat. Monument; 1.57962° S, 36.44730° E; 979 m;

Figures 33–36: *Euplectrus laphygmae* Ferrière: (33) male, lateral, and (34) female, dorsal habitus; (35, 36) male and female, head frontal.

18 Jun. – 2 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, nr OI Keju Nyiro River; SMNH. • 2♀, 1♂; Oloitokitok, 2.94456° S, 37.50714° E, 1853 m; 9–23 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE, SMNH. • 2♀; Elsamere Conservation Centre; 0.81306° S, 36.31585° E; 1913 m; 22 Aug. – 5 Sep. 2019; R. Copeland; MT, Lake Naivasha lacustrine forest remnant; ICIPE. • 1♀; Matthews Range; 1.00661° N, 37.38631° E; 1006 m; 29 Nov. – 12 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, Sarara campsite, shrubland; ICIPE. – **Nairobi Prov.** • 1♀; ICIPE campus, Kasarani; 1.22317° S, 36.89653° E; 1600 m; 10–17 Jun. 2014; R. Copeland; MT, nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub/grassland; ICIPE. • 1♀; Karura forest; 1.24129° S, 36.83277° E; 1672 m; 21 Nov. – 2 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, outside indigenous forest; ICIPE. – **Nyanza Prov.** • 1♀; Mbita; 0.44690° S, 34.20036° E; 1158 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous woodland patch; ICIPE. • 1♂; Ungoye, ICIPE field station; 0.61528° S, 34.09114° E; 1157 m; 12–26 Jun. 2017; R. Copeland; MT inside seasonally swampy forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 2–16 Oct. 2017; R. Copeland; MT inside seasonally swampy forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Mbita; 0.44690° S, 34.20036° E; 1158 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous woodland patch; ICIPE. – **Western Prov.** • 1♀; Khalaba village; 0.4306° N, 34.5468° E; 1365 m; 9–20 Jan. 2016; J. Bukhebi; sweep net in and around homestead in farmland; ICIPE.

ETHIOPIA • 2♀; Nasareth; 11 Jul. 2010; Z. Yefremova; MT; SMNH.

Distribution. Malawi, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda, Zimbabwe (Ferrière 1941); Cameroon, Congo, Ivory Coast (Herting 1976); Kenya (Gerling & Limon 1976); Cape Verde Islands, Tanzania (Fry 1989); Benin, Nigeria (Delvare & Rasplus 1994); China (Zhu & Huang 2003); Indonesia (Ubaidillah 2003); India, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea and Vietnam (Yefremova 2017); *Ethiopia.

Hosts. Ectoparasitoids of the African armyworm *Spodoptera exempta* (Walker, 1956) (Ferrière 1941) and other Noctuidae, as well as Arctiidae (Lepidoptera) (Herting 1976; Gerling & Limon 1976; Fry 1989; Delvare & Rasplus 1994).

Euplectrus liparidis Ferrière, 1941

Figs 37–40

Euplectrus liparidis Ferrière, 1941: 43.

Diagnosis are given by Ferrière (1941) and Zhu and Huang (2003) [without a redescription].

Yefremova (2017) redescribed female (Figs 37, 39): “POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Vertex with 2 long setae between posterior ocelli. Antenna. F1 2.4× as long as broad, F1=F2=F3, F2 and F3 2.2× as long

Figures 37–40: *Euplectrus liparidis* Ferrière: (37, 38) female and male, lateral habitus; (39) female, dorsal habitus; (40) male, head frontal.

as broad, F4 1.1× shorter than F3 and 2.0× as long as broad. Clava 1.3× as long as F4 and 2.1× as long as broad. Head black including cheeks. Lower face yellow from toruli until clypeus, clypeus yellow. Scutellum with longitudinal sculpture. Petiole 2.0× as long as broad. Legs yellow, tbs₁ 1.4× as long as tbs₂. Gaster 1.3× as long as broad.” Body length 1.6–2.2 mm. **Male.** Antenna with bright white colour of scape. F1 2.4× as long as broad, F2 and F3 2.2× as long as broad, F4 2.0× as long as broad. Clava 1.3× as long as F4 and 2.1× as long as broad (Figs 38, 40). Body length 1.3–1.5 mm.

Hansson and Schmidt (2018: 21–22) provided the following diagnosis: “female with frons below level of toruli completely pale, pale area reaching from eye to eye; midlobe of mesoscutum without median groove or carina; reticulation on scutellum with elongate meshes; without groove between dorsellum and scutellum; female gaster with pale area in anterior part as a round spot about as wide as ½ the width of gaster.”

Material examined. Syntype: ALGERIA • 1♀; Algiers, Bou Zegza; Sep. 1936; M. Delassus; *Euplectrus liparidis* sp. n. Ch. Ferrière det.; NHM51238.

KENYA—**Coast Prov.** • 1♀; Shimba Hills Nat. Park, Makadara Forest; 4.23783°S, 39.39567°E; 436 m; 24 Sep. – 8 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Shimba Hills Nat. Park, Longomwagandi Forest; 4.23456°S, 39.41687°E; 389 m; 24 Sep. – 8 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Chawia forest; 3.47908°S, 38.34162°E; 1614 m; 10–24 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; SMNH. • 1♀ same data; 18 Sep. – 2 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 7–21 Aug. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasigau Mtn, bottom of forest; 3.82080°S, 38.64178°E; 737 m; 19 May – 2 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Ngangao Forest; 3.36100°S, 38.34186°E; 1848 m; 18 Sep. – 2 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Mwata area; 3.48444°S, 38.33251°E; 1011 m; 10–24 Aug. 2011; R. Copeland; MT below Bura Bluff, riverine forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Arabuko-Sokoke forest, 80 m; 3.30958°S, 39.96538°E; 31 Dec. 2014 – 13 Jan. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; SMNH; 1♀; same data; 21 Jul. – 3 Aug. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasigau Mtn, indigenous forest; 3.82374°S, 38.65831°E; 1376 m; 24 May – 7 Jun. 2018; R. Copeland; MT along forest path to summit; ICIPE. — **Eastern Prov.** • 1♀; Kibwezi Forest; 2.41687°S, 37.95388°E; 945 m; 13–27 Jan. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Njuki-ini Forest; 0.51663°S, 37.41852°E; 1471 m; 19 Sep. – 3 Oct. 2016; R. Copeland; MT just inside indigenous forest; ICIPE. — **Nairobi Prov.** • 1♀; Karura Forest; 1.24129°S, 36.83277°E; 1672 m; 2–9 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, outside indigenous forest; SMNH. • 1♀; same data; 9–16 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, outside indigenous forest; SMNH. — **Nyanza Prov.** • 1♀; Mbita, nr Lake Victoria; 0.44690°S, 34.20036°E; 1158 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous woodland patch; ICIPE. — **Rift Valley Prov.** • 1♀; Sarara camp-

site; 1.00661°N, 37.38631°E; 1006 m; 29 Nov. – 2 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland; ICIPE. • 1♀; Matthews Range; 0.97984°N, 37.34599°E; 1459 m; 5–19 Apr. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest nr Wamba; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 19 Apr. – 3 May 2016; SMNH. • 1♀; same data; 3–17 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest nr Wamba; SMNH. • 1♀; Oloito-kitok; 2.94456°S, 37.50714°E; 1853 m; 9–23 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 23 Dec. 2011 – 6 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; SMNH. • 1♀; nr Malu Farm, Naivasha; 0.62884°S, 36.42966°E; 1909 m; 10–25 Oct. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in understory of Yellow *Acacia* stand; ICIPE. — **Western Prov.** • 1♀; Kakamega Forest, nr Lukusi River, 2.2 km NE of KFS headquarters; 0.25557°N, 34.87367°E; 1566 m; 19 Apr. – 3 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT; ICIPE.

Distribution. Algeria (Ferrière 1941); Czech Republic, Italy (Zhu & Huang 2003); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Ectoparasitoid of caterpillars of Noctuidae (Zhu & Huang 2003) and Erebidae Yefremova (2007).

Comments. The Kenyan specimens have a whitish scape, and whitish fore coxae, femora and tibiae as does the syntype (Hansson and Schmidt (2018: 23) mentioned as holotype) (Figs 37, 38). They differ from the examined syntype in the length of tbs₁ (1.6× as long as T1 vs. tbs₁ 1.4× as long as T1), clava 1.5× as long as F4 (1.3× in syntype) and in the variation in the length of petiole 1.8–2.0× as long as broad (2.0× in syntype).

Euplectrus nigrescens Ferrière, 1941
Figs 41–44

Euplectrus nigrescens Ferrière, 1941: 35.

Diagnosis given by Ferrière (1941), Zhu and Huang (2003) and Yefremova (2007) without redescription. Additional characters. **Female** (Figs 41–44). Scape 5.4–5.6× as long as broad, F1 1.1× as long as pedicel. POL 2.0× as long as OOL. Mid lobe of mesoscutum with complete, shallow medial groove and with medial carina running along bottom of groove for posterior ½ of groove (Figs 42, 43). Head and thorax entirely black, clypeus dark brown to black (Fig. 44), legs yellow (Fig. 41). Body length 1.8–2.0 mm. **Male.** Similar to female in colour and morphology.

Material examined. Syntype: SOUTH AFRICA — **Western Cape Prov.** • 1♀; Mossel Bay, Witzenberg Valley; Dec. 1921; R.E. Turner; *Euplectrus nigrescens* Ch. Ferrière det.; NHM 010370929.

KENYA • **Coast Prov.** • 1♀, 1♂; Kasigau Mtn; 3.82667°S, 38.64982°E; 1117 m; 13–27 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to spring in forest; ICIPE. — **Eastern Prov.** • 1♀; Kasaala area; 2.07836°S, 38.22517°E; 733 m; 19 Nov. – 3 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE; 1♀; same

Figures 41–44: *Euplectrus nigrescens* Ferrière, female: (41, 42) lateral and dorsal habitus; (43) dorsal head and thorax, mesoscutum with arrow pointing to complete medial groove and 0.2 distal part with carina at bottom (arrowed); (44) head frontal and thorax lateroventral.

data; 26 Jan. – 9 Feb. 2016, R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE. – **Nyanza Prov.** • 1♀; Ungoye, ICIPE field station; 0.61528° S, 34.09114° E; 1157m; 15–29 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT inside seasonally swampy forest; SMNH. – **Western Prov.** • 1♀; Kakamega Forest, nr KFS headquarters; 0.23742° N, 34.86607° E; 1620m; 30 May – 12 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; SMNH.

Distribution. South Africa (Ferrière 1941); China, Venezuela (Zhu & Huang 2003); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus nigroclypeatus Ferrière, 1941
Figs 45–48

Euplectrus nigroclypeatus Ferrière, 1941: 37.

Diagnosis. Female. Mesoscutum with posterior medial groove for $\frac{1}{3}$ length of mesoscutum, without carina. POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Scape 5.0–5.2× as long as broad, F1 1.8× as long as broad, F2, F3 and F4 1.9× as long as broad, clava 2.0× as long as broad and 1.4× as long as F4. Body length 1.7–1.9 mm.

Male. Scape 4.2× as long as broad, F1 1.8× as long

as broad, F2 1.6× as long as broad, F3 1.6× as long as broad, F4 1.6× as long as broad, clava 2.3× as long as broad and 1.6× as long as F4. Body length 1.5 mm.

Description. Female. Body length 1.4 mm.

Colour (Figs 45, 47). Body mostly black, head black, clypeus black, mandibles and labial segments yellow, eyes dark red, ocelli brown, antenna yellow, tegulae yellow, gaster yellow on Gt₁₋₄, brownish on Gt₅₋₇, legs yellow.

Head (Fig. 48). Malar sulcus absent. Two long setae present on vertex between posterior ocelli. Eyes asetose. POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Antennae inserted at the level of the lower margin of the eyes. Scape 5.2× as long as wide (Fig. 46). Pedicel 2.5× as long as broad and 1.1× as long as F1. F1 1.2× as long as F2=F3=F4. F2, F3 and F4 1.8× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 2.0× as long as broad and 1.4× as long as F4.

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mesoscutum areolate with posterior medial groove $\frac{1}{3}$ its length, without medial carina, scutellum reticulate and axillae smooth, propodeum smooth, with medial carina and semicircular transverse cup, callus with two rows, first with 4 setae, second with 2 setae. Fore wing 2.7× as long as broad. smv with 3 long setae.

Figures 45–48: *Euplectrus nigroclypeatus* Ferrière, female, syntype NHM01030947: (45) labels; (46, 47) lateral and dorsal habitus; (48) head frontal.

Speculum small. smv(55):mv (65):pmv (40):stv (25); pmv 1.6× as long as stv. Costal cell bare and with one row of 5 setae close to marginal vein. Hind legs with two spurs; tbs₁ 2.1× as long as T1 and 1.9× as long as tbs₂.

Metasoma. Petiole 1.2× as long as broad, reticulate. Gaster 1.1× as long as broad.

Male. Body length 1.5 mm.

Colour similar to female. POL 1.5× as long as OOL. Scape 4.2× as long as broad, F1 1.8× as long as broad, F2 1.6× as long as broad, F3 1.6× as long as broad, F4 1.6× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 2.3× as long as broad and 1.6× as long as F4. Petiole 1.2× as long as broad, reticulate. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines.

Material examined. Syntype: SOUTH AFRICA – **Western Cape Prov.** • 1♀; Mossel Bay; 31 Jul. 1921; R.E. Turner; *Euplectrus nigroclypeatus* Ch. Ferrière det.; NHM01030947.

BURUNDI • 1♀; Rusizi Nat. Park, degraded bush/grassland; 3.34364°S, 29.27246°E; 774m; 26 Feb. – 10 Mar. 2010; R. Copeland; MT near 3 small trees; ICIPE.

ETHIOPIA • 1♀; Jinka; 10 Aug. 2010; Z. Yefremova; yellow pan trap; SMNH.

KENYA – **Coast Prov.** • 1♀; Shimba Hills Nat. Park, Longomwagandi Forest; 4.23456°S, 39.41687°E; 389m; 31

Jul. – 13 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 24 Sep. – 8 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; SMNH. • 2♀; same data; 25 Oct. – 5 Nov. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; SMNH. • 1♀; same data; 19 Nov. – 3 Dec. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; SMNH. • 1♂, Shimba Hills Nat. Park, Makadara Forest; 4.23783°S, 39.39567°E; 436m; 24 Sep. – 8 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside indigenous forest; SMNH. • 3♀; Mrima Hill Forest; 4.48576°S, 39.25845°E; 212m; 13–28 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. • 5♀, 1♂; same data; 27 Jun. – 11 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. • 1♀; Taita Hills, Chawia Forest; 3.47908°S, 38.34162°E; 1614m; 10–24 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 25 Jul. – 8 Aug. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 8–22 Aug. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 3♀, 3♂ same data 22 Aug. – 5 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 4♀, 4♂; same data; 5–19 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 3–17 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to small forest pond; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kaya Kinondo, indigenous forest; 4.39382°S, 39.54567°E; 10m; 25 Dec. 2011 – 8 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, coral rag canopy forest; ICIPE. • 1♂; Taita Hills, Mwatate area; 3.48444°S, 38.33251°E; 1011m; 24 Jan. – 7 Feb. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Diani Beach area; 4.27559°S 39.59337°E; 10m; 22 Mar. – 12 Apr. 2014; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland off Diani

Beach road; ICIPE. • 1♀; Arabuko-Sokoke Forest; 3.30958°S, 39.96538°E; 80 m; 25 Sep. – 12 Oct. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; ICIPE. • 1♂; same data; 16–30 Nov. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in bush outside forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Buda Forest; 4.46109°S, 39.40446°E; 98 m; 6–20 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 28 Aug. – 20 Sep. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. – **Eastern Prov.** • 2♀; Ngaia Forest; 0.32442°N, 38.05038°E; 1057 m; 3–17 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT inside bottom of indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 20 Aug. – 3 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT inside bottom of indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 24 Dec. 2011 – 7 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT inside bottom of indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasaala area; 72.07836°S, 38.22517°E; 33 m; 24 Apr. – 8 May 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE. • 1♂; Nyambene Hills, Itieni Forest, at bottom; 0.24433°N, 37.87016°E; 2142 m; 18 Sep. – 2 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest nr forest station; ICIPE. • 1♀; Njuki-ini Forest; 0.51663°S, 37.41852°E; 1471 m; 27 Jun. – 11 Jul. 2016; R. Copeland; MT just inside indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Mulu Musingila farm; 2.11412°S, 38.23989°E; 689 m; 11–25 May 2018; R. Copeland; MT, farmland next to seasonally wet area; ICIPE. – **Nairobi Prov.** • 1♂; ICIPE campus, Kasarani; 1.22317°S, 36.89653°E; 1600 m; 18 Apr. – 2 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub/grassland; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 10–15 Jun. 2017; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub/grassland; ICIPE. – **Western Prov.** • 1♂, 2♀; Kakamega Forest, nr KFS headquarters; 0.23742°N, 34.86607°E; 1620 m; 18 Apr.

– 3 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 2–16 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 16–30 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 30 May – 12 Jun. 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; 4 Jul. 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Malava Forest; 0.46372°N, 34.885727°E; 1619 m; 4–8 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; SMNH.

Distribution. South Africa (Ferrière 1941); *Burundi, *Ethiopia, *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus rufiventris Ferrière, 1941
Figs 49–52

Euplectrus rufiventris Ferrière, 1941: 37.

Diagnosis was provided by Ferrière (1941). **Female.** Mesoscutum without medial groove and medial carina, reticulate. Scutellum alutaceous. POL 2.5× as long as OOL. Ocelli small. Two setae between posterior ocelli. Antenna. Scape 4.5× as long as broad, pedicel 1.1× shorter than F1, F1 1.2× as long as F2, F2=F3=F4, clava 1.8× as long as broad. Petiole 1.5–1.6× as long as broad. Head black with light brown clypeus. Thorax black, tegulae yellow (Figs

Figures 49–52: *Euplectrus rufiventris* Ferrière: (49, 50) male and female, lateral habitus; (51) dorsal habitus; (52) head and thorax, frontolateral.

50, 52), gaster entirely yellow including tip, except sometimes with small lateral spots. Antennae yellow, sometimes light brown. All legs yellow. **Male.** Head black, clypeus reddish brown (Fig. 51). Antenna. Scape 4.0× as long as broad. Clava slightly brownish (Fig. 49), 2.1× as long as broad. Body length 1.5–1.8 mm.

Material examined. Syntype: SOUTH AFRICA – **Western Cape Prov.** • ♀; Mossel Bay; Jul. 1921; R.E. Turner; *Euplectrus rufiventris* Ch. Ferrière det.; NHM 010370920.

KENYA – **Coast Prov.** • 2♀; Kasigau Mtn, bottom of forest; 3.82080°S, 38.64178°E; 737 m; 2–16 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. • 1♂; Kasigau Mtn indigenous forest; 3.82667°S, 38.64982°E; 1117 m; 30 Jun. – 13 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT next to spring in forest; ICIPE. • 1♀, 1♂; Diani Beach area; 4.27559°S, 3.59337°E; 10 m; 4–18 Feb. 2014; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland off Diani Beach Rd; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; except 17 Feb. – 2 March, 2014; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland off Diani Beach Rd; ICIPE. • 2♀; Gede Forest; 3.30946°S, 40.01941°E; 19 m; 21 Jul. – 3 Aug. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; SMNH. • 1♀; Buda Forest; 4.46109°S, 39.40446°E; 98 m; 11–25 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; SMNH. – **Eastern Prov.** • 1♀; base of Endau Mtn; 1.30026°S, 38.52805°E; 531 m; 22 Feb. – 7 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; same data; except 23 Jan. – 6 Feb. 2017; R. Copeland MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kasaala area; 2.07836°S, 38.22517°E; 733 m; 19 Feb. – 4 Mar. 2019; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; ICIPE. • 1♀; Kiboko Sanctuary; 2.20331°S, 37.71430°E; 925 m; 25 Aug. – 5 Sep. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. • 1♀; Mulu Musingila farm; 2.11412°S, 38.23989°E; 689 m; 27 Apr. – 11 May 2018; R. Copeland; MT, farmland nr small, seasonally wet area; ICIPE. • 1♀; Nyambene Hills, at bottom of Itieni forest; 0.24433°S, 37.87016°E; 2142 m; 13–27 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest nr Forest Station; ICIPE. • 1♀, 1♂; Marsabit Forest; 2.32167°N, 37.98409°E; 1418 m; 4–18 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT nr Ahmed gate, indigenous forest; SMNH. – **Rift Valley Prov.** • 1♀; Tsavo West Nat. Park, riverine woodland; 2.99615°S, 38.45988°E; 464 m; 30 Jul. – 12 Aug. 2008; ICIPE. • 2♀; same data; 12–26 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo River; ICIPE. • 1♂; Nguruman, nr Sampu River; 1.90117°S, 36.05040°E; 723 m; 5–19 Jun. 2011; R. Copeland; MT; SMNH. • 2♀; Matthews Range, Sarara campsite; 1.00061°N, 37.38631°E; 1006 m; 9–23 Jan. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, shrubland; SMNH.

Distribution. South Africa (Ferrière 1941); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus scapus Yefremova, 2007
Figs 53–58

Euplectrus scapus Yefremova, 2007: 351.

Diagnosis. **Female** (Figs 53, 58). POL 4.0–4.5× as

OOL (Fig. 58). Diameter of posterior ocelli large 3.0× longer than OOL (Figs 54, 58). Scape 5.0× as long as broad, F1=F2, F3=F4, clava 2-segmented 2.5× as long as broad. Medial lobe of mesoscutum with incomplete posterior groove (as in male in Fig. 56) $\frac{2}{3}$ length of mesoscutum, strongly areolate. Scutellum superficially reticulate, with 2 pairs of long setae. Propodeum smooth, with medial carina and large cup. Fore wing 2.6× as long as broad, pmv about 1.5× as long as stv. Gaster 1.6× as long as broad. Body length 1.5–2.5 mm.

Male. Antenna (Figs 54, 55, 57) with swollen oblong scape, 2.0–2.1× as long as broad and with centrally situated ventral plaque 0.3× as long as scape. F1 1.2× as long as F2, F3=F4, clava 2-segmented 2.6× as long as broad. Fore wing 2.6× as long as broad, pmv about 1.5× as long as stv. Gaster 1.3× as long as broad. Body length 1.5–2.1 mm.

Additional characters. **Female.** POL 4.0–6.0 OOL, mean = 5.2 (n=10), diameter of posterior ocellus 3.0–3.2× as long as OOL. Ocelli much larger than those in other species. Hind coxae brown or brownish. **Male.** POL 2.2–3.5 OOL, mean = 2.9 (n=10), diameter of posterior ocellus equal to diameter of anterior ocellus, 1.0–1.4× as long as OOL. Hind coxae brown, brownish or dark yellow in small specimens (Figs 53, 54).

Material examined. KENYA – **Kitui** • 1♂; Sosoma area; 4–18 Dec. 2019; R. Copeland; MT; ICIPE.

UAE – **Sharjah** • 164♀, 12♂; Sharjah Desert Park; 20 Oct. – 8 Nov. 2005; A. van Harten; LT; SMNH.

Distribution. Israel (Yefremova 2015b); UAE (Yefremova 2008); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus singularis Ferrière, 1941
Figs 59–62

Euplectrus singularis Ferrière, 1941: 38.

Diagnosis was given by Ferrière (1941). Mid lobe of mesoscutum areolate with posterior groove $\frac{1}{3}$ of its length, without carina, scutellum finely reticulate. **Female.** POL 1.75× as long as OOL. Diameter of posterior ocelli small and 1.3× less than OOL (Fig. 61). Scape 4.8× as long as broad. Pedicel equal to F1. F1 equal to F2 and F3 to F4. Clava 2-segmented 2.6× as long as broad and 1.5× as long as F4. Body length 1.96 mm. **Male.** Mesoscutum areolate with short medial carina posteriorly, propodeum with medial carina smooth. Scape 2.2× as long as wide (Fig. 62) with large, concave sensory area. F1–F4 almost equal to each other and 1.7× as long as broad. Clava 4.0× as long as broad and 1.7× as long as F4 (Fig. 62). tbs₁ equal to T1, which 1.8× as long as tbs₂.

Figures 53–58: *Euplectrus scapus* Yefremova: **(53)** female, paratype, lateral habitus (not to scale); **(54, 55)** male, lateral and dorsal habitus; **(56)** female, dorsal, close-up of head and thorax with medial groove arrowed; **(57)** male, closeup of head and thorax; **(58)** female, frontal.

Redescription. Male. Body length 1.6 mm.

Colour. Body mostly black, head dark brown, antenna yellow and brownish on the top, petiole black, gaster pale brown; legs yellow, fore and mid coxae whitish, hind coxae dark yellow (Fig. 59).

Head. Malar sulcus present. Eyes asetose. POL 1.75× as long as OOL. Diameter of ocelli 2.2× shorter than OOL. Scape swollen, 2.0× as long as wide with large concave sensory area (Fig. 62). Pedicel 1.8× as long as broad, with two long yellow setae. F1=F2,

F3=F4; all funiculars 1.55× as long as broad. Clava 2-segmented (Fig. 60), 2.6–2.8× as long as broad and 1.6× as long as F4.

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mid lobe of mesoscutum areolate with posterior groove 1/5 of its length; scutellum finely reticulate, propodeum smooth, with medial carina, callus with 8 setae. Fore wing 3.0× as long as broad. smv with 3 long setae. Speculum small and narrow along mv. Smv(30):mv (70):pmv (32):stv(23); pmv 1.4× as long as stv. Cos-

tal cell with row of 8 setae close to marginal vein. Hind wing rounded apically.

Metasoma. Petiole 1.6× as long as wide; gaster 2.0× as long as broad.

Material examined. Syntype (Fig. 59): UGANDA • 1♂; Kampala; Mar. 1927; G.L.R. Hancock; ex reticulated cocoon; *Euplectrus* ♂ (PLT) *singularis* Ferrière, det. Z. Bouček, 1974; NHM 013457193.

KENYA – Coast Prov. • 1♀, 1♂; Taita Hills, Ngangao Forest; 3.36100°S, 38.34186°E; 1848m; 19 Apr. – 3 May 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE; 1♀; same data; 19 Sep. – 3 Oct. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE.

Distribution. Uganda (Ferrière 1941); *Kenya.

Host. Lepidoptera (Pieridae) *Belenois creona* (Cramer, 1776).

Figures 59–64: (59–62) *Euplectrus singularis* Ferrière: (59) labels of male syntype NHM013457193; (60) male, lateral habitus, not to scale; (61) female, lateral habitus; (62) male, frontal. (63, 64) *E. subsphaericus* sp. n., lateral habitus: (63) female, holotype; (64) male.

Euplectrus subsphaericus sp. n.

Figs 63–65

LSID. [urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:AD181BF6-53EE-402B-9FA5-89C668E9B0C6](https://zoobank.org/act:AD181BF6-53EE-402B-9FA5-89C668E9B0C6).

Etymology. This species is named for the subspherical shape of the male scape.

Diagnosis. Female. Mesoscutum without medial

groove and medial carina, strongly areolate. POL 2.8× as long as OOL. Antenna (Fig. 63). Scape 5.6× as long as wide. Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad, with 2 long yellow setae. F1 and F2 2.2× as long as wide, F3 and F4 2.4× as long as wide. Clava 2-segmented 3.0× as long as wide and 1.4× as long as F4. Body length 1.25–1.30 mm. **Male.** POL 2.9–3.0× as long as OOL. Antenna (Figs 64, 65). Scape 1.4× as long as wide with large concave sensory area (Fig. 65). Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad. F1 2.5× as long as wide, F2

Figures 65–70. (65) *E. subsphaericus* sp. n., paratype, male, Kenyan specimen, head on card. (66–70) *E. turneri* Ferrière: (66) labels of female syntype NHM01030916; (67) female, lateral habitus, not to scale; (68) male, lateral habitus, Kenyan specimen, not to scale; (69, 70) female, dorsal habitus and head frontal, not to scale.

and F3 2.0× as long as wide, F4 2.2× as long as wide. Clava 2-segmented 3.2× as long as broad and 1.6× as long as F4. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines. Body length 1.2–1.4 mm.

Description. Female. Body length 1.25–1.30 mm (HT 1.25 mm).

Colour: body mostly black, head brown, clypeus brownish, mandibles and labial segments yellow, eyes dark pink, ocelli dark yellow, antenna yellow, radculus black, tegulae yellow, gaster yellow on Gt₂₋₃, brownish on Gt_{1,4-6}, legs pale yellow, hind leg coxae dark yellow.

Head. Malar sulcus absent. Several long pairs of setae present on vertex. Eyes aetose. POL 2.8× as long as OOL. Antennae inserted at level of lower margin of eyes. Scape 5.6× as long as wide. Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad, with 2 long yellow setae and equal to F1. F1 and F2 2.2× as long as wide, F3 and F4 2.3× as long as wide. Clava 2-segmented 3.0× as long as wide and 1.4× as long as F4.

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mesoscutum without medial groove and medial carina, strongly areolate. Axillae finely reticulate. Scutellum strongly areolate. Propodeum. Callus with two rows, first with 4 setae, second with 2 setae. Fore wing 2.5× as long as broad. smv with 3 long setae. Speculum small and narrow along pterostigma. smv(26):mv(54):pmv(23):stv(16); pmv 1.4× as long as stv. Costal cell bare and only row with 6 setae close to marginal vein. Hind wing rounded apically. Hind legs with two spurs; tbs₁ 1.6× as long as T1 and 1.4× as long as tbs₂.

Metasoma. Petiole 1.7× as long as broad, reticulate. Gaster 1.8× as long as broad.

Male. Body length 1.2–1.4 mm. Colour as in female.

Head. Malar sulcus absent. Mandibles without teeth. Several long pairs of setae present on vertex. Eyes aetose. POL 2.9× as long as OOL. Antenna (Fig. 64). Scape 1.2–1.4× as long as wide with large concave sensory area (Figs 63, 64). Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad, with 2 long yellow setae. F1 2.5× as long as wide, F2 and F3 2.0× as long as wide, F4 2.2× as long as wide. Clava 2-segmented 3.2× as long as broad and 1.6× as long as F4. Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate. Mesoscutum without medial groove and carina, strongly areolate, scutellum strongly areolate, axillae finely reticulate, propodeum with weak reticulation, with medial carina and semicircular transverse cup, callus with two rows, first with 4 setae, second with 2 setae. Fore wing 2.5× as long as broad. Metasoma. Petiole 1.7× as long as broad, reticulate. Gaster 1.6× as long as broad. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines.

Holotype. D.R. CONGO – Mayombe • ♀; Luki Biosphere Res.; 5°37'16.7"S, 13°05'54.8"E; 266 m; 24 Sep. 2007; D. Debakker, J.P. Michiels; canopy fogging; SMNH.

Paratypes. D.R. CONGO – Mayombe • 2♀, 5♂; Luki Biosphere Res.; 5°37'16.7"S, 13°05'54.8"E; 266 m; 24 Sep. 2007; D. Debakker, J.P. Michiels; canopy fogging; SMNH.

KENYA – Eastern Prov. • 1♂; Kirimiri Forest nr top of hill; 0.42563°S, 37.54660°E; 1664 m; 12–26 May 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE.

Distribution. Congo, Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

Euplectrus turneri Ferrière, 1941
Figs 66–70

Euplectrus turneri Ferrière, 1941: 36.

Diagnosis. Female. Mesoscutum without medial groove and medial carina, strongly areolate. Antenna. Scape 4.7× as long as broad, F1 1.7× as long as broad, F2 and F3 1.3× as long as broad, F4 1.0× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 2.1× as long as broad and 2.1× as long as F4. Body length 1.5–1.9 mm. **Male.** Antenna. Scape 4.2× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 2.8× as long as broad and 2.1× as long as F4. Genitalia. Digitus with 2 spines. Body length 1.5–1.9 mm.

Redescription. Female. Body length 1.7 mm.

Colour (Figs 68, 69). Body mostly black, head black, clypeus black, mandibles and labial segments yellow, eyes dark brown, ocelli brown, antennal scape pale yellow or whitish, rest of antenna brownish, tegulae yellow, gaster brownish on Gt₂₋₃, brown on Gt₁ and Gt₄₋₇, legs yellow.

Head (Fig 70). Malar sulcus absent. POL 1.8× as long as OOL. Antennae (Fig. 68) inserted at the level of the lower margin of the eyes. Scape 4.7× as long as wide. Pedicel 2.0× as long as broad. F1 1.1× as long as F2 = F3 = F4. F1 1.7× as long as broad, F2 and F3 1.3× as long as broad, F4 1.0× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 2.1× as long as broad and 2.1× as long as F4.

Mesosoma. Pronotum finely reticulate with posterior carina. Mesoscutum without medial groove and medial carina, strongly areolate, scutellum reticulate with longitudinal stripes, smooth in middle and axillae smooth, propodeum smooth, with medial carina and semicircular transverse cup, callus with 4 setae. Fore wing 2.7× as long as broad. smv with 3 long setae. Speculum $\frac{3}{4}$ along mv. smv(45):mv(85):pmv(32):stv(22); pmv 1.5× as long as stv. Costal cell bare and with one marginal row of 3 setae close to marginal vein. Hind legs with two spurs; tbs₁ 1.3× as long as T1 and 1.33× as long as tbs₂.

Metasoma. Petiole small and transverse. Gaster 1.1× as long as broad.

Male (Fig. 68). Body length 1.5 mm. Colour as in female. Scape 4.2× as long as broad, pedicel 1.7× as

long as broad, F1 2.5× as long as broad, F2 and F3 1.3× as long as broad, F4 1.1× as long as broad, clava 2-segmented 1.9–2.0× as long as broad and 2.1× as long as F4. Gaster 1.5× as long as broad. Genitalia. Digitus with two spines.

Material examined. Syntype: SOUTH AFRICA – **Western Cape Prov.** •6♀; Mossel Bay; Apr. – Jun. 1921; R.E. Turner; *Euplectrus turneri* Ch. Ferrière det.; NHM010370916.

KENYA – Central Prov. •1♀; Kamwana Forest; 0.40009° S, 37.38403° E; 1842 m; 1842 m; 14–28 Mar. 2015; R. Copeland; MT in indigenous forest; ICIPE. •1♀; Mary Muriuki farm, farmland nr Nyamindi River; 0.49250° S, 37.38822° E; 1457 m; 2 Jun. – 28 Jul. 2018; R. Copeland; YPT; ICIPE. •1♀; Mary Muriuki farm; 0.49250° S, 37.38822° E; 1457 m; 2–16 Jun. 2018; R. Copeland; MT nr Nyamindi River; ICIPE. •3♀, 1♂; same data; 16–30 Jun. 2018; R. Copeland; MT nr Nyamindi River; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 30 Jun. – 14 Jul. 2018; ; R. Copeland; MT nr Nyamindi River; SMNH. – **Coast Prov.** •6♀, 2♂; Taita Hills, Ronge Forest; 3.21° S, 38.25° E; 1200 m; 25 Oct. – 8 Nov. 1999; Taita Biodiversity Project; MT, nr spring; ICIPE. •5♀, 2♂; Shimba Hills Nat. Park, Longomwagandi Forest; 4.23456° S, 39.41687° E; 389 m; 23 Sep. – 8 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; SMNH. •1♀; same data; 23 Oct. – 5 Nov. 2008; R. Copeland; MT just inside forest; SMNH. •4♀; Taita Hills, Mwatate area; 3.48444° S, 38.33251° E; 1011 m; 7–21 Feb. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, below Bura Bluff, riverine forest; ICIPE. •1♂, 1♀; same data; 27 Jul. – 10 Aug. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, below Bura Bluff, riverine forest; ICIPE. •1♀, 2♂; Kasigau Mtn, indigenous forest; 3.82700° S, 38.64875° E; 1065 m; 28 Dec. 2011 – 11 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT next to campsite in forest; SMNH. •1♂, 1♀ Kasigau Mtn, bottom of forest; 3.82080° S, 38.64178° E; 737 m; 30 Jun. – 13 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. •5♀; same data; 13–27 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 21 Sep. – 5 Oct. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, woodland with grass; ICIPE. •1♀; Mrima Hill Forest; 4.48576° S, 39.25845° E; 212 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 25 Dec. 2011 – 8 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; ICIPE. •3♀; same data; 27 Jun. – 11 Jul. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; SMNH. •1♀; Gede Forest; 3.30946° S, 40.01941° E; 19 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 25 Dec. 2011 – 8 Jan. 2012; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous secondary growth forest; ICIPE. •1♂; Muhaka Forest; 4.32664° S, 39.52462° E; 41 m; 1–15 Mar. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 11–25 Oct. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; ICIPE. •3♀; Muhaka Forest; 4.32471° S, 39.52326° E; 39 m; 23 Mar. – 6 Apr. 2018; R. Copeland; Migration trap, insect flying into forest; ICIPE. – **Eastern Prov.** •2♀, 1♂; Samburu Nat. Reserve, nr Ewaso Ng'iro River; 0.56797° N, 37.53563° E; 874 m; 4–18 Sep. 2007; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest, next to KWS Headquarters; ICIPE. •1♂; Njuki-ini Forest; 0.51663° S, 37.41852° E; 1471 m; 29 Dec. 2007 – 4 Jan. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, just inside indigenous forest; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 29 Sep. – 13 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, just inside indigenous forest; SMNH. •2♀; Kibwezi Forest; 2.41687° S, 37.95388° E; 945 m; 24 Feb. – 9 Mar. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 23 Mar. – 6 Apr. 2016; R. Copeland; MT,

edge of indigenous forest; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 6–20 Apr. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; ICIPE. •2♀, 1♂; same data; 20 Apr. – 4 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 3–17 Jun. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, edge of indigenous forest; SMNH. •1♀; base of Endau Mtn; 1.30026° S, 38.52805° E; 531 m; 28 Nov. – 12 Dec. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest; SMNH. •1♀; Mulu Musingila farm; 2.11412° S, 38.23989° E; 689 m; 29 Dec. 2017 – 12 Jan. 2018; R. Copeland; MT, farmland nr small, seasonally wet area; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 11–25 May 2018; R. Copeland; MT, farmland nr small, seasonally wet area; ICIPE. •1♀; Kiboko Sanctuary; 2.20331° S, 37.71430° E; 925 m; 3–17 Nov. 2011; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous forest edge; SMNH. •1♂; Sosoma area; 0.86344° S, 38.67907° E; 489 m; 2–9 Jun. 2018; R. Copeland; MT, *Acacia commiphora*, woodland; SMNH. •1♀; Kasaala area; 2.07836° S, 38.22517° E; 733 m; 8–22 Jan. 2015; R. Copeland; MT inside isolated woodland patch; SMNH. – **Nairobi Prov.** •1♀, 1♂; ICIPE campus, Kasarani, 1.22317° S, 36.89653° E; 1600 m; 24 Feb. – 10 Mar. 2014; R. Copeland; MT nr stream, meadow in degraded shrub/grassland; ICIPE. •1♀; Karura Forest; 1.24129° S, 36.83277° E, 21–23 Nov. 2017; 1672 m; R. Copeland; 6 m MT just outside indigenous forest; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; MT just outside indigenous forest; 21 Nov. – 2 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; ICIPE. – **Nyanza Prov.** •1♀; Mbita; 0.44690° S, 34.20036° E; 1158 m; 13–27 Nov. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous woodland patch; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT, indigenous woodland patch; SMNH. •1♀; Ungoye, ICIPE field station; 0.61528° S, 34.09114° E; 1157 m; 27 Nov. – 11 Dec. 2017; R. Copeland; MT inside seasonally swampy forest; ICIPE. – **Rift Valley Prov.** •3♀; Tsavo West Nat. Park, riverine woodland; 2.99615° S, 38.45988° E; 464 m; 30 Jul. – 12 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo river nr Nat. Park Gate; ICIPE. •3♀; same data; 12–26 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo river nr Nat. Park Gate; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 7–21 Oct. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo river nr Nat. Park gate; ICIPE. •2♂; same data; 25 Oct. – 8 Nov. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo river nr Nat. Park gate; ICIPE. •2♀; same data; 4–18 Nov. 2008; R. Copeland; MT, bank of Tsavo river nr Nat. Park Gate; ICIPE. •1♂; Matthews Range; 0.97984° N, 37.34599° E; 1459 m; 19 Apr. – 3 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT, riverine forest nr Wamba; SMNH. •2♀; Matthews Range; 1.00661° N, 37.38631° E; 1006 m; 29 Nov. – 12 Dec. 2015; R. Copeland; MT, mixed grass-/woodland; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 28 Dec. 2015 – 9 Jan. 2016; R. Copeland; MT, mixed grass-/woodland; ICIPE. •1♀; same data; 17–31 May 2016; R. Copeland; MT, mixed grass-/woodland; ICIPE. •1♀; Chorlim, base of Mt Elgon; 1.03149° N, 34.84780° E; 1887 m; 22 Apr. – 6 May 2017; R. Copeland; MT in *Acacia* riverine woodland; SMNH. •1♀; Masai Mara Nat. Reserve; 1.54638° S, 35.30672° E; 1756 m; 25 Jul. – 8 Aug. 2008; R. Copeland; MT next to dry stream bed; ICIPE. •1♀; Lake Nakuru, Nat. Park; 0.47203° S, 36.06388° E; 1908 m; 6–20 Jan. 2006; R. Copeland; MT, mixed *Olea*, *Vepris*, *Cussonia* woodland; SMNH.

Distribution. South Africa (Ferrière 1941); Yemen (Yefremova 2007); *Kenya.

Host. Unknown.

DISCUSSION

Of the 14 Kenyan species of *Euplectrus*, seven were sampled in less than five sites (Table 1; Figs 71, 72; see also [Supplementary material](#)). Of these seven species, four were collected from a single sampling site. Five species were collected at 15 or more sampling locations, and two species were collected in 8 and 12 sites respectively. *Euplectrus laphygmae* and *E. turneri* were collected in the most locations (29

and 27 respectively). It is interesting to speculate about the significance of the marked differences in geographical distribution among these species. Possible differences may reflect differential responses to Malaise traps. Some species may simply behave in such a way that it is a rare event when they are captured. Species may be mono- or oligophagous and their appearance would necessarily depend on their host's phenology. This may be the case with those species that were collected in one, or few, areas.

Figure 71: Distribution of species of the genera *Euplectromorpha* and *Euplectrus* in Kenya.

Although all our data result from the passive sampling of insects captured in Malaise traps, using the temporal and geographical data for each species could inform field workers where and when they may expect to find particular species on the wing. The exposed state of the host may facilitate the collection of *Euplectrus*-infested caterpillars in the field and provide the opportunity of productive rearing in the laboratory.

Nearly all host records of *Euplectrus* are from exposed Lepidoptera caterpillars. The dominant host groups are Geometridae and Noctuidae, some of which are serious pests of cultivated plants. For example, *Euplectrus* attacks *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith, 1797) larvae (Fall Army Worm [FAW]) in India. Recently, FAW invaded Africa and should *Euplectrus* also parasitize FAW in Africa, the accurate identification, to the species level, of parasitoids

Figure 72: Distribution of species of the genus *Euplectrus* in Kenya.

Table 1. Summary of occurrences of *Euplectrus* species in Malaise trap sites and their range of elevation above sea level.

Species	Number of sites	Min. elev., m	Max. elev., m	Median elev., m
<i>E. aburiensis</i>	8	615	2162	940
<i>E. cinctiventris</i>	5	80	1887	1006
<i>E. epiplemae</i>	3	98	1117	737
<i>E. fuscipes</i>	1	1882	1882	1882
<i>E. icipeensis</i> sp. n.	15	464	2507	1620
<i>E. laphygmae</i>	29	10	2162	1567
<i>E. liparidis</i>	17	80	1909	1376
<i>E. nigrescens</i>	3	733	1145	1117
<i>E. nigroclypeatus</i>	19	5	2142	1006
<i>E. rufiventris</i>	12	10	2142	711
<i>E. scapus</i>	1	501	501	501
<i>E. singularis</i>	1	1848	1848	1848
<i>E. subsphaericus</i> sp. n.	1	1664	1664	1664
<i>E. turneri</i>	27	19	1908	1011

effective in control of FAW or other lepidopteran pests could be important for successful biological control efforts. The present paper is essential for the identification of *Euplectrus* adults.

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Supplementary material. A list of georeferenced localities mentioned in this article (Figs 71, 72) with species collected therein: [10.5281/zenodo.15838022](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15838022).

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